

Website Traffics Acquisition Model for E-Business using Search Engine Optimisation and Sitemap Submission (SEOSS)

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Abstract—It is inevitable to accept that today's business trends focus on selling products online using the latest web application system and website marketing tools. This phenomenon creates a high competition on search engine ranking among website owners in gaining business leads, visitor traffics and acquisitions. This paper proposed a model on improving e-business traffics acquisitions in terms of the number of new visitors (traffics) and returning visitors using Search Engine Optimization (SEO) and Sitemap Submission. This method has been tested on two different online business websites. The detailed results are discussed in the results and discussion section. It is recommended that the SEO strategy implementation is needed for e-business website.

Keywords—High Ranking Search Engine, Web Analytics, e-Commerce Marketing, Online Business Strategy

I. INTRODUCTION

The Rapid expansion of digital world in interactive media and World Wide Web (WWW) [1] requires businesses and entrepreneurs to explore more on selling their products and services online. Almost everything that is needed is now available on the internet. With a single keyword or phrase search in the search engine, hundreds of search results are retrieved that show online business websites and blogs. There are many advantages of selling products online as opposed to traditional, bricks-and-mortar retail practices. Identifying products for possible purchase and making price comparisons among available reseller require significantly less time and effort in a digital marketplace than the physical world [1][2].

The growth of economic power in Asia Pacific Region also brings a positive impact, together with globalization, web technology and broadband penetration. Asia has shown a great potential of internet marketing and e-business activities due to the increase of internet users in Asia represent 48.2% of total number of World Internet users by region in 2015 (Fig. 1) [3]. From a marketing perspective, the impact of the increase of internet users has manifested itself primarily in two ways [adoption of ecommerce], first, an increase in the number of companies seeking to use the world wide (WWW) to communicate with potential customers, and second, the rapid adoption of the WWW by a broad segment of consumers for a variety of purposes, such as pre-purchase research and online shopping [5]. These two factors lead to substantial growth of

the use of internet and WWW as the main medium of online business activities.

Fig. 1. World Internet Users by Region [3]

In Malaysia, a total of 5.3 Billion businesses have registered with Suruhanjaya Syarikat Malaysia (SSM) in 2013 [4]. Most companies create their website to showcase their products and services with the use of e-commerce system or e-Business portal system. In addition, e-commerce allows local businesses the ability to penetrate international markets that used to be difficult to enter due to high transaction costs and other market access barriers [5]. With the increase number of online businesses, the biggest challenge for business who had invested on developing e-commerce website and portal is how to market their website to specific and targeted customers to gain continuous profits by selling online. The targeted customers who seek for a product or service must browse specific websites which offer the required product and service. For example, if a customer is looking for a 'Therapy Machine', the customer should visit a website which specifically sells a Therapy Machine rather than other machines. In this case, users or customers may use web search tools to look up pre-purchase product information (price, design, style, reviews etc.), even if the transaction is finally

executed offline [6]. Search engines have quickly become the primary web search tools since its existence in 1994 [7], due to the facts that consumers able to use powerful search tools free of charge to easily find and compare product and shopping information on the internet [6]. Therefore, to answer the challenge on how businesses can market their website to targeted customers is rely on their *website presence in the search engine*, their *website position* in search engine ranking and *relevancy of the website* with customers' queries.

The importance of website presence in the search engine, website positioning and relevancy of the website to customer's queries increase the business website acquisition. Website traffics acquisition enable website owner to understand the performance of the website from which the traffics or visitors they received came from. Website acquisition information is gained and analyzed using web data analytics tools such as Google Analytics. The website acquisition data is categorized based on the channel or source of visitors, which are; All Traffics, Google AdWords, Search Engine Optimization, Social networking and Campaigns [8]. These traffics and visitors are important for any business as they will eventually convert to sales and profits for the businesses.

In this research, we proposed a model to enhance website presence and position in search engine to increase website traffics acquisition for e-business website with the adoption of search engine optimization (SEO) strategy and sitemap link submission. The model has been applied to two e-business websites and the web traffics acquisition for these two websites has been monitored for two phases where each phase takes a period of six months for that year. The research expects the increase number of website acquisition especially the number of new user based on Organic Search result.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Overview of Search Engine

Search engine is intelligent software used to find any information in World Wide Web and present the result in various form with advanced findings. Currently, there are two types of search engine; search engine and web directory. Search engine result is based on search engine result pages (SERP) which have the combination of various forms such as website, picture, and book while web directory is focused on classification and subcategories. The main difference between them is search engine is more independent in receiving all information while web directory accumulates information by individuals [9]. At present, there are few popular and active search engines for examples Yahoo, Google, MSN, Bing, AOL and others. According to comScore, about 64 percent users used Google in February 2016 and chose Google Site as their preferred search engine³. Nowadays, users prefer search engine that provides a noble experience in information searching. In business online industry, for example, the owners ensure that their websites are listed in every search engine and rank in most popular list. Marketing online businesses and products in search engine has become emerging industry in the developed world [10]. [11] suggests that Search Engine Marketing (SEM) can be categorized in two main categories which are Search Engine Optimization (SEO), which has various methods on how to get a good rank

in the organic result section on Search Engine Result Page (SERP), and Paid Search or Pay Per Click (PPC) services offered by most of the search engine companies. Paid Search or PPC involves bidding on certain keywords to get higher ranking in the advertising section. This method involves an amount of marketing budget to get a good position in SERP. Most of the time, an advertiser is charged only when web visitors click on their advertisement [11]. In this research, authors will use the advantages of free SEO services and techniques with combination of free Sitemap submission services available online in getting website acquisitions. Therefore, the proposed methods will not incur any marketing costs for business owner to get more website visitors.

B. Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

Search engine optimization (SEO) is a technique to increase the visibility of viewer's view by obtaining the highest-ranking website in the search result list. Due to the frequent changes of website contents, the website ranking is triggered as a new requirement from certain search engines. The ranking process used SEO is free and mostly listed and ranked based on the most relevant to users. Basically, search engine uses crawler or spider as an agent to crawl in network. The agent finds the most up to date information and finally rank and index the information. SEO then takes place with appropriate technique in turn to produce applicable indexed website. SEO is applied in various areas in turn to enhance the capability, recognition, relevancy and significance of information gathered. [12] find that SEO is one of valuable technique to boost up the headlines on online news in journalism industry. [13] claim that the response towards online advertisement using SEO for business marketing has increased and getting more customers. However, the result of ranked website is divergent from several websites.

[14] described the groups of techniques used in Search Engine Optimization such as Directory Submission, Keyword Generation and Link Exchanges. [15], has established a conceptual framework of Search Engine Optimization. The framework, classifies optimization techniques under two broad categories: white hat and black hat SEO. The white hat optimizations techniques are further categorized by: keyword research, indexing, on-page, and off-page optimization, whereas black hat optimization techniques are divided under two categories: content spam and link spam. [15], discussed the Search Engine Optimization strategy in maximizing the organization of the traffic retailer receivers through product searches on search engine. The first and most common SEO strategies is to tweak a site in an attempt to increase the rank of a retailer's organic link on the results pages for a given search term. It was known as a "black-hat strategy" based on "tricking" or "spamming". A second and most costly SEO strategy focuses on improving site quality and brand awareness. [16], presents that Search Engine Marketing (SEM) is applied to increase search engine visibility of a web site. There are two clearly distinctive types of SEM; Search Engine Optimization and Search Engine Advertising (SEA). The different techniques related to SEO are keyword discovery, crawling, on-page and off-page optimization. [17] on the other hand, presents both Search Engine Optimization and Search Engine Advertising are the most relevant search engine

marketing activities. Search engine optimization deals with three main components of search engine algorithms which are the text component, the link component and the popularity component.

C. Sitemap Submission

Sitemap is a smart tool to help user to understand the whole concept of website. [18] finds a sitemap is a structured list of webpages. The sitemap assist user in navigating the website in efficient way with logical representation overview in separate category¹¹. Traditionally, sitemap is normal HTML files that outline various structures in hierarchal view. Today, Google has introduced XML sitemap as one of innovative approach to utilize the sitemap function. Unlike normal SEO, the XML sitemap practices a Google Webmaster Tool whereby use the crawler or spider to search for the files that have been submitted in sitemap and then ranked to the most relevant.

However, not all submitted files are chosen and ranked [18]. Only the good authority, reputation and trusted files are prioritized to be indexed and ranked [19][23]. Besides the three items, it is necessary to ensure that the submitted documents are verified with suitable qualification and updated contents with unique information thus letting more website to be linked and more files to be indexed by Google [21]. By utilizing this, the traffic growth is increased and more visitors visit the targeted website. Therefore, this technology with the collaboration of SEO to enhance e-business website acquisition especially on traffics growth is demonstrated in this study. The research has reviewed several of the most useful search engine sitemap submission tools. The search engine sitemap submission services can be divided into two categories which are Manual Sitemap Submission and Automatically Sitemap Submission. Table 1 presents the example of sitemap submission services for both categories.

TABLE I. Major Sitemap Submission Tools and Services

Major Sitemap Submission Tools and Services	
Manual	1. Google - https://www.google.com/webmasters/tools/submit-url 2. Bing - http://www.bing.com/toolbox/submit-site-url 3. Yandex - http://webmaster.yandex.com/addurl.xml 4. Baidu - http://zhazhang.baidu.com/sitesubmit/index 5. RSS Feed - http://feedburner.google.com/fb/a/ping 6. Asks.com - http://asks.com
Automatic	1. Attracta - http://www.attracta.com 2. Clever Submitter - http://www.cleversubmitter.com 2. Free Web Submission - http://www.freewebsubmission.com 3. Entire Web - http://www.entireweb.com/free_submission

The manual sitemap submission requires website owner or webmaster to manually enter their website address into each of the sitemap submission box provided in the sitemap submission tool. Meanwhile, the automatic sitemap submission allows website owner to automatically submit their website sitemap to various search engine like google.com, alexa.com, baidu.com, yahoo.com and others, with a single click. Based on the literature review and testing on the features available in all stated tools above, the research has selected the automatic sitemap submission tool, Attracta.com as the sitemap submission tool for this research study. Its feature that uses the Google recommended XML

sitemap protocol, enables to boost listing to major search engine such as Bing, Yahoo!, Ask and Google, and verifies up to 1,000 pages submitted.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology in design and implementation of the website traffics acquisition model for e-business using search engine optimisation (SEO) and sitemap submission. Firstly, with the advance features of SEO and sitemap submission in increasing website ranking in search engine, the researchers identified the suitable SEO techniques for most online business owner. This is to ensure that this model can be applied by most of e-business website. The research has identified and adopted most important SEO strategy recommended by [22]. WebCEO has categorized the SEO analysis in four main criteria as shown in TABLE II. These four SEO criteria have been technically implemented in the two sample websites.

TABLE II. SEO Criteria and Rules Implementation

SEO Criteria	SEO Rules Implementation
1.On-Site Issues	All pages of the website must have Unique Title Tags, Unique Description Tags, H1 Headings, XML Sitemap and Robots.txt
2.Landing Page SEO	Keywords must have in Title Tags, Keywords with size H1, H2 and H2 must be in Headings, Keywords in description tags, Keywords in Body pages, Keywords in URL, Keywords in image ALT Tags and image filename.
3.Page Speed SEO	Size of images must be optimized, Minify HTML, Minify CSS and JavaScript, Enable compression, Leverage Browser Caching, Reduce server response, Avoid landing page redirects.
4.Mobile Optimization	Website must be mobile friendly and responsive design. Mobile page speed must follow Google recommended page speed score.

Secondly, the research has proposed the use of an automatic sitemap submission offered by Attracta [23] due to its ability to boost listing to major search engine such as Bing, Yahoo!, Ask and Google. It also applied the Google recommended XML sitemap protocol and most importantly it is free. Attracta recommends using the sitemap submission tool on weekly basis for best result.

Therefore, the research has scheduled to perform the sitemap submission once a week, which is on every Friday at 2PM along the research time frame. The process of sitemap submission require researcher to open the Attracta website and create account, then register the address of the website to be submitted.

Fig. 2. Attracta Sitemap Submission View

Lastly, researcher need to click the *Create and Submit Sitemap* link provided in the tools. The Attracta automatically Creates, Published, Verified, Submit the sitemap and Check for acceptance of the website submission to be indexed on four main search engines namely, Google, Yahoo!, Bing and Ask.com. Fig. 2 shows the Attracta Sitemap Submission View.

The traffics data from these two websites were analyzed and modeled to determine the result of SEO implementation and sitemap submission applied to the sample websites towards the enhancement of traffics acquisition. The traffics acquisitions parameters that the research focuses are:

- Number of New Visitor
- Number of Returning Visitor
- Traffic Channel (Source) – Organic Search
- Device Category uses by Visitor

The Number of New Visitor refers to the first-timer visitor that visit the sample websites, while the Returning visitor refers to exiting visitor that revisit the website to make further action like purchasing or researching products. Traffic channel is the source or from where the user come from, it can be from referral website, social website like Facebook and Instagram, direct source where user directly type the website URL in browser or Organic Search describes the actual query string entered by a user from a web search [8].

The website acquisition data were collected and analyzed by using web data analytics tool called Google Analytics. Google analytics is a data analytics tools provided by Google which able to report website’s visitor logs such as visitor’s location, time of access, source of visitors, length of time visits and others [8]. To reach the data, the two website samples have been configured and registered with the Google Webmaster tool [25]. The time frames of data collection and analysis for these two websites have been divided into two phases where each phase takes a period of six months for that year. The first phase was from June 1, 2014 to December 31, 2014, and the second phase was from January 1, 2015 to June 30, 2015.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section describes the results of this research. Firstly, based on the overall process of implementing SEO and sitemap submission to the two sample websites, the research able to illustrate the Website Traffics Acquisition Model for E-Business as in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Website Traffics Acquisition Model with SEO and Sitemap Submission

In this model, e-Business website is configured to follow the search engine optimization which focuses on four main criteria; On-site Issues, Landing Page SEO, Page Speed SEO and Mobile Optimization. Then, the model suggests implementing the sitemap submission using Attracta automatic sitemap submission. The frequency of sitemap submission is once a week during the research time frame. The data were collected and analyzed by using web data analytics tool called Google Analytics. To received web data logs in Google Analytics, the sample website is registered in Google Webmaster Tool at first hand.

The second part of result and discussion section describes the analysis result based on the website data logs in Google Analytics. In this case, the total number of New Visitors, Returning Visitors, Traffic Channel Source (Organic Search) and Device Uses of the two sample websites, Site A and Site B were first tabulated. The search engine was Google.com.my and the time frame for first phase was from June 1, 2014 to December 31, 2014, and the second phase was from January 1, 2015 to June 30, 2015. The rationale for focusing on Google as the data source for organic search was because Google seamlessly connects the ranking of the web pages, and currently Google is the largest search engine in the world [26].

Table III shows the general statistics of the two websites’ total visitors in two phases. For Site A, the total numbers of visitors increased almost 10 times for phase 2 compared to phase 1, from 581 visitors to 5597 visitors. In phase 1, site A recorded its new visitor of 484 or 83.30% and returning visitor of 97 or 16.70% in the same duration. Returning visitor is important to measure whether the new visitor is revisiting the website for next purchase.

TABLE III. Web Traffics Acquisition for New Visitor and Returning Visitor for Site A and Site B

	Total Visitors	New Visitor	Returning Visitor	Percentage of New Visitor	Percentage of Returning Visitor
SITE A					
Jun 1, 2014 – Dec 31, 2014	581	484	97	83.30%	16.70%
Jan 1, 2015 – Jun 30, 2015	5597	5047	550	90.17%	9.83%
SITE B					
Jun 1, 2014 – Dec 31, 2014	1117	1034	83	92.57%	7.43%
Jan 1, 2015 – Jun 30, 2015	1326	1124	202	84.77%	15.23%

Meanwhile, phase 2 shows dramatically increase in number of visitors for Site A where 5047 or 90.17% of new visitors was recorded and 550 of the visits are from the same visitors. Site B shows a small increase number of visitor of

209 visitors from phase 1 (1117) to phase 2 (1326). Phase 1 recorded 1034 or 92.57% of new visitor with 7.43% of the new visitor were returning visitors to the website. In Phase 2, 84.77% of visitors are new visitors and 15.23% of visitors are returning visitors. The increase of number of visitors from phase 1 and phase 2 show the positive impact of the applied model.

Table IV shows the percentage of number of visitors based on Organic search. Organic search is used to measure the effectiveness of the SEO and sitemap submission for this study. It shows how the search engine rank our website in the search engine based on relevancy of keywords contained in our website and user queries. The effectiveness of SEO and sitemap submission help in getting good search engine ranking. Site A recorded a total of 120 or 20.65% visitor comes from organic search in search engine as compared to other channel like website referral, direct visitor to website and social networking site.

TABLE IV. Web Traffics Acquisition for Traffic Channel by Organic Search

SITE A	Total Visitors	Organic Search	Other Channel (Referral, Direct, Social)	Percentage of Organic Search	Percentage of Other Channel
Jun 1, 2014 – Dec 31, 2014	581	120	461	20.65%	79.35%
Jan 1, 2015 – Jun 30, 2015	5597	696	4901	12.44%	87.56%

SITE B	Total Visitors	Organic Search	Other Channel (Referral, Direct, Social)	Percentage of Organic Search	Percentage of Other Channel
Jun 1, 2014 – Dec 31, 2014	1117	783	334	70.10%	29.90%
Jan 1, 2015 – Jun 30, 2015	1326	957	369	72.17%	27.83%

However, visitors from organic search has increased in phase 2 about 696 visitors to indicate that website impression has increased in most of the search engine especially Google.com.my. Site B also shows a good indication where the number of visitors from organic search in search engines has increase from 783 in phase 1 to 957 visitors in phase 2. The research concludes that the SEO implementation and sitemap submission bring positive impact in search engine ranking.

Table V shows the web traffics acquisition based on devices category. This is to show whether the model implemented suggested different result in website acquisition on device categories. There are three device categories that the research has analyzed which are; Mobile, Desktop and Tablet. Site A show that most of their visitors were using Mobile

device which recorded 365 visitors or 62.82%, followed by Desktop users with 192 visitors and Tablet user with 24 visitors.

Meanwhile, in phase 2, the number has changed where most of the visitors were coming from Desktop user with about 3635 visitors and least was still Tablet users with only 179 visitors. Site B has recorded the same pattern with site A where the highest number of visitors recorded from Mobile visitors in phase 1 was 530 visitors and it changed to the highest number of visitors to Desktop visitors with 631 visitors in phase 2. However, Tablet visitors for Site B recorded as the least number of visitors for both phases with 111 visitors and 171 visitors. This result indicates that the model implemented gave a better impression result in Desktop compared to Mobile.

TABLE V. Web Traffics Acquisition based on Device Categories

SITE A	Total Visitors	Mobile	Desktop	Tablet
Jun 1, 2014 – Dec 31, 2014	581	365 (62.82%)	192 (33.05%)	24 (4.13%)
Jan 1, 2015 – Jun 30, 2015	5597	1783 (31.86%)	3635 (64.95%)	179 (3.20%)

SITE B	Total Visitors	Mobile	Desktop	Tablet
Jun 1, 2014 – Dec 31, 2014	1117	530 (47.45%)	476 (42.61%)	111 (9.94%)
Jan 1, 2015 – Jun 30, 2015	1326	524 (39.52%)	631 (47.59%)	171 (12.90%)

V. CONCLUSION

This research discusses on how to increase web traffic acquisition for e-business website by using Search Engine Optimization (SEO) and Sitemap Submission. The research has reviewed several best practices of SEO strategy and sitemap submission to be applied in the proposed model. The research discovered and adapts four best practices of SEO strategy from an industry leading SEO organization to be applied in sample website. An automatic sitemap submission called Attracta.com has been selected as the sitemap submission tools in this research. The sitemap of the two sample websites have been submit and create once a week during the research period which has been divided in two phases. The result of the research towards two sample websites, Site A – An online web service offering and Site B – Women Apparels and Accessories Marketplace has been discovered in result section.

The overall result indicates the increase number of new visitors and returning visitors for both Site A and Site B from phase 1 to phase 2. The number of visitors based on organic search shows a dramatic increase for Site B from 120 visits to 696 visits, and slightly increases for Site B from 783 visits to 957 visits. This indicates that the SEO implemented for sample website has increase the website ranking in search engine that increase the website impression through organic search. Finally, web traffic acquisition based on device categories shows that most of the visits were from Desktop users, followed by Mobile and Tablet users for both Site A and Site B.

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